

Extraction of Liquid Fertiliser from Urine Using Microbial Fuel Cells: A Sustainable Solution for Hydroponics in Circular Cities

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Abstract

For a circular economy, sustainable reuse and recycling of resources are vital strategies. This study builds on proof-of-concept research demonstrating the transformation of urine into treated filtrate containing NPK nutrients, water, and energy. It assesses the suitability of catholyte, produced by electro-filtrating microbial fuel cells (EF-MFCs), for hydroponic plant cultivation. The results showed that the MFC reactor recovered nutrients such as potassium, phosphorus and nitrogen in the form of liquid (catholyte) in previously empty chamber and simultaneously produced electrical energy (1.5-2 mW) from synthetic urine. Catholyte mixed in varying proportions with standard nutrient solution and used neat was evaluated for basil growth, wet, and dry biomass. Results showed a 60/40 nutrient solution-to-catholyte mix was most effective, highlighting EF-MFCs' potential for sustainable agricultural applications.

Keywords

basil; catholyte; human urine; hydroponics; liquid fertiliser; microbial fuel cell

INTRODUCTION

Urine is a rich source of nitrogen and phosphorus, essential nutrients for plant growth, and has historically been used as fertiliser (Udert et al., 2006). However, hygiene and safety concerns have limited its widespread adoption. Recycling urine offers significant sustainability benefits, including reduced climate impacts, water usage, and eutrophication (Martin et al., 2023). Recent advancements, such as solid fertiliser production from urine (Ren et al., 2021), highlight its potential, but scalable, integrated approaches are still needed.

Microbial fuel cells (MFCs) provide a promising solution for urine recycling by generating electricity and recovering nutrients. MFCs with ceramic membranes produce high-pH catholyte through electro-osmotic drag (Gajda et al., 2015, 2019), which is rich in nutrients and suitable for agricultural applications like hydroponics. This approach is energy-efficient and aligns with sustainability goals, particularly for resource-limited settings.

Using MFC-derived catholyte in hydroponics could reduce reliance on synthetic fertilisers while enabling circular nutrient management. However, challenges such as ensuring consistent quality, plant compatibility, and public acceptance must be addressed. Hydroponic farming in controlled environments, such as vertical farming, offers efficient and sustainable food production, closer to consumers.

This study evaluates the potential of catholyte produced from synthetic urine in MFCs as a bio-fertiliser for hydroponic cultivation, focusing on basil. Key properties of the catholyte, including pH and COD removal, will be examined to optimise its application in sustainable farming systems.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Microbial fuel cell setup and operation

Six MFCs were constructed in two groups and ceramic cylinders were made in-house using terracotta clay (Bath Potters, UK), with dimensions of 8 ± 0.5 cm (H), 1.5 cm (internal diameter), and 0.2–0.25 cm wall thickness. The anode was made of carbon veil coated with activated carbon and PTFE (5% w/w), with a loading of 5 mg/cm², while the cathode was prepared with activated

carbon and 20% PTFE (w/w), hot-pressed, and cut to a final size of 21 cm².

The electrodes were placed onto the ceramic membrane in polypropylene containers, with catholyte extraction tubes leading to a 1L collection bottle. Each anode chamber had a working volume of 70 ± 5 mL and was fed continuously with synthetic urine medium (242 mL/day) via a peristaltic pump. The first group of MFCs operated under open-circuit (OC) conditions, while the second operated under closed-circuit (CC) conditions with external loads of 100 or 50 ohms, later unified to 50 ohms after day 210. All anodes were inoculated with activated sewage sludge (Wessex Water, UK).

Hydroponics cultivation of basil

The experiment was conducted at the Envirotron greenhouse (Frenchay Campus, University of the West of England) from May to June 2020, using a randomised 3 × 6 design with five nutrient solutions (100/0, 90/10, 80/20, 60/40, 0/100) and a control (blank; no catholyte addition), each with three replicates. Greenhouse conditions were maintained at 25 °C (day), 15 °C (night), and 62 ± 15% humidity.

Sweet basil (*Ocimum Basilicum*) seeds were sown in 25 × 25 × 40 mm rockwool cubes (Sonenlory, UK), hydrated with sterile distilled water (SDW), and covered with sifted vermiculite. Germinated seedlings were initially irrigated with 200 mL SDW and hydrated weekly with 40 mL. When cotyledons fully expanded, uniform seedlings were selected for hydroponic cultivation.

Collected catholyte was pooled and added to nutrient solutions. Seedlings were placed in trays with biweekly replenishment of nutrient-catholyte mixes, while SDW was added every 2–3 days to maintain moisture.

Tested liquid fertiliser conditions

Nutrient solutions were prepared to match the phosphorus demand for 6 weeks of basil growth (150 mg total, 25 mg/week). Macronutrients (N, P, S, K, Mg, Ca) were added in a ratio of 6:1:2:7:1:5 using NH₄NO₃, CaCl₂, KCl, MgSO₄, and KH₂PO₄. The pH was adjusted to 7.0 using HCl.

Treatments were labelled based on the ratio of standard nutrient solution to MFC catholyte, calculated by phosphorus content. For instance, a 60/40 ratio indicates 60% of phosphorus was supplied by the nutrient solution and 40% by catholyte.

Table 1. Tested conditions in various ratios of standard nutrient solution and MFC catholyte mix.

Treatment		Blank	100/0	90/10	80/20	60/40	0/100
Added catholyte (mL/week)		0	0	6	10	20	40
Added elements from standard nutrient solution (mg/week)	N	0	150	132	120	90	0
	Ca	0	125	110	100	75	0
	K	0	150	132	120	90	0
	S	0	50	44	40	30	0
	P	0	25	22	20	15	0

Harvesting and growth assessment

Weekly time-lapse photos were taken using a digital camera (Nikon, Japan) on a tripod. After seven weeks, leaves, roots, and stems were harvested, and wet and dry weights were measured to evaluate plant growth under each treatment.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Catholyte production and characteristics

Figure 1. Catholyte recovery in relation to MFC power generation over 300 days of operation. OC denotes the open-circuit group, while CC denotes the closed-circuit group. On Day 210, external loads were connected to the cells in the OC group. The symbols represent the mean values of the triplicates, with errors indicated by error bars.

The working MFCs in the closed-circuit group demonstrated stable power generation over 300 days of operation, achieving consistent power output ranging between 1.5 mW (power density, P_D : 21.4 W/m^3) and 2 mW (P_D : 28.6 W/m^3) per cell. After day 210, the OC group was also connected to external resistors (50 Ω), which then produced similar levels of power output as the CC group. This continuous and stable power generation in the working MFCs suggests potential applications for powering auxiliary devices such as pumps or lights in a scaled-up hydroponic system.

There was a distinctive difference in catholyte production between the OC and CC groups. Reactors in the OC group typically produced less than 1 mL/day of catholyte, whereas the CC group produced 4–5 times more catholyte in volume. The characteristics of the produced catholyte also differed, with the working MFCs' catholyte exhibiting a higher pH close to 11, compared to the OC group catholyte, which had a pH around 9.5. Additionally, cations such as sodium and potassium were present in higher concentrations in the working MFCs' catholyte compared to the OC group. This demonstrates that catholyte production is closely linked to MFC power generation via electro-osmotic drag, a self-driven process (requiring no external energy input) that enables simultaneous resource recovery from urine and electricity generation.

Basil growth performance

Basil (*Ocimum basilicum*) cultivated with catholyte-enriched nutrient solutions exhibited varied growth responses across treatments. The 60/40 nutrient solution-to-catholyte ratio resulted in the highest plant height (19.7 ± 1.2 cm) and biomass yield. Plants grown under 80/20 and 90/10 conditions also demonstrated comparable growth (18.3 ± 2.6 cm and 17 ± 0.8 cm, respectively), indicating that catholyte supplementation is effective up to a certain threshold.

In contrast, plants grown in 100% catholyte (0/100) exhibited stunted growth (4.17 ± 2.7 cm) compared to the control group (0/0), which only reached 3.7 ± 3.8 cm. The limited growth observed in the pure catholyte group may be attributed to salinity stress from elevated sodium concentrations (5,466 mg/L) or an imbalanced ratio of required nutrients. This finding highlights the need for dilution or blending strategies to mitigate potential toxicity in future applications.

Figure 2. Basil growth assessment in all treatment conditions after 6 weeks.

CONCLUSION

This study demonstrates the feasibility of using MFC-derived catholyte as a sustainable biofertiliser in hydroponic systems. The 60/40 nutrient solution-to-catholyte ratio was most effective for basil cultivation, supporting growth and biomass production while reducing dependency on synthetic nutrients. Addressing challenges such as salinity and phosphate recovery will be critical for scaling this technology. These findings highlight the potential of MFCs to contribute to circular economy initiatives by integrating waste treatment with sustainable agriculture.

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